

A study of pollen viability and longevity in *Oryza rufipogon*, *O. sativa*, and their hybrids

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The length of pollen viability after anther dehiscence is crucial to successful pollination (Stone et al 1995), particularly for outbreeders. It determines the possibility of outcrossing between species, provided that limited specific reproductive barriers exist. With the rapid development of biotechnology, more transgenic crops, including transgenic rice, are becoming available, resulting in biosafety concerns about possible ecological risks. Evaluation of transgenes introgressing to wild rice species becomes an important issue for rice breeders, environmentalists, and policymakers. Studying pollen viability and longevity of wild and cultivated rice species as well as their hybrids is important in evaluating outcrossing frequencies.

Identifying a suitable method is the key to a more accurate estimation of pollen viability (Rodriguez-Riano and Dafni 2000). In rice, the common approach to estimating pollen fertility is to examine mature pollen

stained with iodine-potassium iodide solution (I_2 -KI). In vitro germination for pollen fertility has also been used but difficulties in obtaining an optimal culture medium were reported (Khatun and Flowers 1995). We conducted experiments on screening various culture media to estimate pollen viability and longevity after dehiscence of *Oryza rufipogon*, *O. sativa*, and their hybrids over time. We also compared pollen viability immediately after anther dehiscence with pollen fertility obtained using I_2 -KI staining to understand the relationships of the two data sets.

Oryza rufipogon was collected from a natural population in Chaling, Hunan Province, China. Seeds of rice cultivar Minghui 63 were donated by Prof. S.M. Mu from the Hubei Academy of Agricultural Science and hybrids were obtained from crosses between *O. rufipogon* (female) and Minghui 63 (male) in 1999. The three taxa were grown

in the experimental field of the Genetics Institute of Wuhan University in 2000. For pollen fertility estimation, fresh and mature pollen grains were examined under the microscope 10 min after staining with 1% I_2 -KI solution. Culture media with different components were screened (Table 1) for optimal pollen germination. Pollen grains with different time intervals after anther dehiscence—i.e., 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, 10, 13, 15, 18, 20, 25, 30, 35, and 40 min—were germinated in a petri dish with about 1.5 mm of ply glutin medium. The number of germinated pollen grains was scored under the microscope 1 h after incubation at 34 °C.

P4, P5, and P6 culture media gave the highest percentage germination (Table 1). P5 was selected for subsequent pollen germination. We also found that a higher percentage of rice pollen germinated at temperatures ranging from 25 to 40 °C, with the highest germination rate at 34 °C.

Table 1. Components of different culture media used in the experiment and their effect on pollen germination of *O. rufipogon*, Minghui 63, and their hybrids.

Code of culture medium	Component				Pollen germination (%) ^a		
	Borax (g)	Sucrose (g)	Glutin (g)	Water (mL)	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Minghui 63	Hybrid
P1	0.1	8	20	100	29.4 f	58.4 f	24.2 e
P2	0.1	8	25	100	35.4 e	67.5 e	25.4 de
P3	0.1	8	30	100	48.7 bc	81.7 abc	30.1 bcd
P4	0.1	12	20	100	55.9 ab	85.2 a	32.3 abc
P5	0.1	12	25	100	58.4 a	84.9 a	33.9 a
P6	0.1	12	30	100	54.3 ab	83.2 ab	32.4 ab
P7	0.1	15	20	100	49.1 b	79.6 bc	30.5 bcd
P8	0.1	15	25	100	40.5 c	77.1 cd	29.1 bcd
P9	0.1	15	30	100	36.3 d	72.3 de	27.2 cde

^aMeans of pollen germination followed by different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$) according to Duncan's multiple range test.

The number of viable pollen at 0 min after dehiscence was much lower than the I₂-KI stainable pollen in the three taxa (Table 2). About 40% of the stainable pollen grains in *O. rufipogon*, 13.5% in Minghui 63, and 50% in the hybrids did not germinate. This indicated that pollen stainability using the I₂-KI staining method did not correctly reflect pollen fertility, and that the method can be used only as a relative measure of fertility.

In the pollen germination experiment, the three taxa showed variable pollen viability at different time intervals and had different half-life (50% loss of pollen viability) rates after anther dehiscence (see figure). Minghui 63 not only had the highest pollen germination rate (approximately 85%) at 0 min after anther dehiscence but also the fastest decline in pollen viability. It lost 50% of viable pollen within 6 min and nearly 100% about 30 min after anther dehiscence. Compared with Minghui 63, *O. rufipogon* had a lower pollen germination rate (approximately 60%), but its pollen viability was much longer, retaining 50% pollen viability after 12 min. Its pollen viability could last for 60–70 min based on regression analysis. The hybrids had the lowest pollen germination rate (approximately 34%) and medium pollen longevity. More than 50% of the pollen grains were viable after 10 min and a few were still viable after 40 min. These results indicated that pollen viability and pollen longevity varied among the three taxa studied. This supports the report by Khatun and Flowers (1995) that rice pollen remains viable for only a short time. Moreover, pollen longevity does not depend on initial pollen viability.

Pollen grains can remain viable for a certain time after anther

Table 2. Relationship between I₂-KI stainable and viable pollen (\pm = standard deviation).

Material	Stainable pollen (%)	Viable pollen (%) ^a	Viable/stainable pollen
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	98.1 \pm 1.72	58.4 \pm 2.76	0.60
Minghui 63	94.0 \pm 2.35	84.9 \pm 2.05	0.87
Hybrid	66.2 \pm 14.5	33.9 \pm 3.41	0.51

^aPercentage of viable pollen was recorded by in vitro germination at 34 °C with pollen grains sampled at 0 min after anther dehiscence.

In vitro pollen germination after anther dehiscence. The nonlinear regression was $Y_{\text{Minghui 63}} = 1.92/(1 + 1.376 \exp^{(0.177x)})$, $R^2 = 0.99$; $Y_{O. rufipogon} = 0.88/(1 + 0.616 \exp^{(0.093x)})$, $R^2 = 0.98$; $Y_{\text{hybrid}} = 0.413/(1 + 0.309 \exp^{(0.179x)})$, $R^2 = 0.99$, respectively.

dehiscence. This time varied among the three taxa studied. Some *O. rufipogon* pollen remains viable even after 60–70 min, indicating the potential for outcrossing with cultivated rice. Our unpublished data showed overlapping flowering time of cultivated rice and *O. rufipogon*, which allows outcrossing between *O. rufipogon* and *O. sativa* to occur if the physical distance between the two is relatively close. In addition, our study showed partially fertile pollen of hybrids (34%), indicating the possibility that any transgene in a partially fertile hybrid can be passed on to its selfed and backcrossed progenies. We believe that, once transgenic rice is available in the environment, transgenes will have good oppor-

tunities to be captured by close relatives of rice such as *O. rufipogon*.

References

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